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EXTERNAL DEBT BURDEN IN NIGERIA: IMPLICATIONS FOR ACHIEVING ZERO HUNGER

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Abstract: On the 31st December 2025 the percentage ratio of Nigeria's external debt servicing to export attained 157% exceeding by large magnitude the World Bank specified critical value of 25%, signaling debt crisis and heavy burden. Hence, this study examined the effects of excessively large external debt servicing and interest payments on government annual budgetary allocation to agriculture in Nigeria as insight into the feasibility of Nigeria meeting the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) of zero hunger in 2030. In this study, external debt service and interest payments on debt served as proxies for burden; while government annual budgetary allocation to agriculture as proxy for meeting zero in 2030. The data were extracted from annual external debt stock, external debt service payments, interest payments on external debt and government expenditures on agriculture from 1970 to 2025. These data were collected from Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN), National Bureau of Statistics (NBS), World Bank data and various sources. To estimate the model, the study employed Auto Regressive Distributive Lag (ARDL) bound test. The results of the analysis indicated that in the short run, which external debt stock and external service had significant negative effect on agriculture; while over the long run external debt stock, external debt servicing and interest payments on external debt had significant negative effect on agriculture. Implications of the findings: 1. Nigeria's external burden from 1970 to 2025 has a depressive effect on agriculture; 2. such adverse effect of external debt on agriculture implied less agricultural infrastructure, technology, fertilizers etc.; 3. less productivity in agriculture and increased food scarcity; 4. Increased hunger and Nigeria's inability to accomplish Sustainable Development Goal of zero hunger in 2030. Hence, the author recommended that government should ensure that all kinds of public borrowing should be project tied, giving more priority to agriculture. Investment in agriculture in Nigeria should be more of transfer of real resources rather than monetary income to avoid inflation among other recommendations.

Keywords: Sustainable Development, Zero Hunger and External Debt Burden

1.1 INTRODUCTION

Since the late 1970s public debt has remained a permanent feature of Nigeria's fiscal sector. Public debt per se is not a problem but the capacity to manage it. Poor management of public debt results in difficulties in generating sufficient proceeds for repayment resulting in debt albatross. At this point public begins to claim

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excessively large portion of the country's export earnings. For instance Nigeria's external debt servicing as at December 2025 was claiming 157% of the country's export earnings, exceeding the critical point of 25 % (World Bank, 2025). This is point at which public debt squeezes government budget and hinders development projects, hence the issue of debt burden.

Nigeria's stock of foreign debt began to witness a gradual build up from \$8.531 billion in 2007 to \$13.13 billion in 2008 representing 54% increase (NBS 2018). By 2016, Nigeria's stock foreign borrowing rose to over \$31 billion. It then implies that between 2007 and 2016 the country's stock of foreign borrowing grew by 244% (Adebola, 2019). Meanwhile, Nigeria's size of external debt service payment rose significantly from \$0.7 billion in 2008 to \$2.5 billion in 2016 representing 257% increase. Interest payment alone rose from \$0.09 billion in 2008 to \$0.6 billion in 2016, representing 567% increase (NBS, 2020). In December 2020, Nigeria's stock of foreign debt stood at N12.7 trillion (Omoisi, 2021). The growing external debt and its servicing obligations in Nigeria, trigger fear of crowding out effect of external debt on agriculture that might worsen food shortage, hunger, and extreme poverty to frustrate Nigeria's chances of accomplishing Sustainable Development Goals in 2030. In Nigeria, agriculture solves the problems of extreme hunger; rising unemployment and acute poverty that occupy number one of Sustainable Development Goals (Omoisi, 2020; Dewette & Navalure, 2013). Hence, the general objective of this study was to examine the effect of external debt burden on sustainable development; while the specific objective is to examine the effect of external debt on agriculture in Nigeria. The outcome of this study would be significant for various reasons. Agriculture is an anchor sector for the meeting of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) of solving the problem of unemployment, core poverty of food shortage and acute hunger in Nigeria. Agriculture is central to diversification exercise in Nigeria. The outcome of this study would serve as a useful document for policy making in agriculture. It would contribute to body literature on agriculture as reference document for future researchers. Hence, the objective of the study is to determine the effect of external debt burden on agricultural output with annual budgetary expenditure on agriculture as a relevant proxy. Other variables for this study are external debt stock, external debt service payments and interest payments on foreign debt. From the ongoing, it is therefore hypothesized; external debt stock and debt service payments as well as interest payments on foreign payments have significant negative effects on agriculture in Nigeria. The rest of this paper is structured as follows: section 2 is review of related literature; section 3 is theoretical framework and methodology; section 4 is presentation and interpretation of results and section 4 is conclusion and implications of results/recommendations.

2.0 REVIEW OF THE RELATED LITERATURE

2.1 Conceptual Literature

External debt becomes a burden when its servicing begins to claim excessively large portion of the country's export earnings. According to World Bank (2025) by December 2025 Nigeria's debt servicing was claiming 157% of export earning signaling heavy debt burden. When external debt begins to limit the ability to invest in agricultural infrastructure, technology, and hinder agricultural productivity, it is a burden. This is focus of this study.

Agriculture according to dictionary definition is a deliberate effort made by man to till the soil and to cultivate crops, rear animals for food and other purposes (Iwena, 2019). For this study, agriculture means annual

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budgetary allocation to agricultural sector. Agriculture in this study means increased budgetary allocation to agriculture and output growth. During the debt crisis of the 1980s in Nigeria, annual budgetary allocations meant for agriculture were diverted to repayment of external debt to avoid closing of international credit lines and debt default. This had long-term negative implications on agriculture.

Sustainable Development Sustainable development is the act of meeting the needs of the present generation without compromising the needs of the future generations. Sustainable development is a trio concept consisting of three aspects of development such as socio-political development, economic development and ecological issues.

Hence, as debt grows (D_t) cost of borrowing(r) increases and debt service payment (rD) follows which depresses investment in agriculture (Agric.). Then recognizing the channels of relationship between external debt outstanding(D_t),interest payment on debt(r),external debt service payment on debt(Ds) and agriculture, the researcher presents the empirical model as:

$$\text{Agric}=\beta_0+\beta_1D_t + \beta_2rD + \beta_3r + \epsilon_2\dots\dots\dots(3.15)$$

Where β_0 =intercept; β_1 to β_3 are coefficient; ϵ_2 =error term

$$D_t <0;rD <0;rD <0; r <0$$

Empirical Literature

Umaru,Ndigife,&Zacharia(2025) examined the effect of domestic debt on economic growth in Nigeria. These authors investigated the influence of public domestic debt service payments and interest payments on debt on investment, aggregate savings and growth. To estimate the model the researchers made use of Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) technique. The results of the analysis indicated that interest payments on debt and debt service payments had significant negative effects on savings, investments and growth in Nigeria.

Sunday,Ogbogbulu, Mba & Onumonu(2025) examined the impact of public debt on economic growth in Nigeria. This study combined external debt and domestic debt to see how interest payments and debt service payments relate with savings, investment and growth in Nigeria. To estimate the model the authors employed Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) Method. The results of the analysis indicated that interest payments on debt and debt service payments had significant negative effect on savings, investments and growth in Nigeria.

Manamba &William (2025) examined the effect of external debt burden on economic growth in Africa. The authors sampled five African countries such as Nigeria, Ghana, South Africa, Cameroun, and Niger republic. Variables such as interest payments on debt, debt service payments, investment and GDP were used for the study. Panel regression method was used for the study .The result of the analysis indicated that interest payments on debt depressed investments in Africa.

John,Nsoja &Gbengi(2024) evaluated the effect of debt burden and revenue leakages on human development in Nigeria. The study investigated how debt burden depressed allocation to education. To estimate the model, the authors employed Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) technique. The results of the analysis indicated that both interest payments on debt and debt service payments depressed investment in education and economic growth in Nigeria.

Musa& Nengi(2025) Examined the effect of public debt on economic growth in Nigeria. The authors captured the following variables in their study: interest payment on debt, service payments, aggregate domestic savings,

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investment and GDP. The researchers employed Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) technique as inferential statistical tools. The results of the analysis indicated that interest payments on debt had significant negative effect on aggregate savings and investments.

3.1 THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK AND METHODOLOGY

3.2 Theoretical Framework

Debt-Agriculture Linkage

The theoretical underpinning in the relationship between external debt and agriculture revolves around debt overhang argument/ investment crowding out hypothesis that states that large external debt discourages investment and raises the fear of rising tax liabilities of domestic investors in the future (Ajayi, 1995). This the theory upon which, Wyplosz (2007) debt sustainability approaches is anchored. This theory states that improper management of debt raises capital output ratio and weakens domestic savings. Then paucity of savings distorts the composition of investments. In addition, poor investments retard growth. The lowering of domestic savings by large public debt creates pressure on budgets as government begins to service large debt. The pressures of debt on budget through servicing depress investment. Hence Charles Wyplosz described debt sustainability as the magnitude of debt burden over a period of time which is equivalent to the ratio of the difference between real cost of borrowing(r) and growth rate(g) to change in debt to GDP ratio minus the ratio of non interest current account balance(NICAB) to change in debt to GDP ratio. Hence the following functional presentation:

$$bt_{bt-1} - r - g/bt-1 - \frac{NICAB}{bt-1} \dots\dots\dots(3.1)$$

A rising external debt (Dt), debt service payments (rD) and cost of borrowing (r) may likely reduce annual budgetary allocation to agriculture and depress investment in agriculture as well as agricultural output which may trigger declining output, hunger, loss of employment and worsening poverty (Rahman, 1969; Chenery&Eckstein, 1970; Ajayi, 1995; Anyanwu, 1998).

The relationship between Dt and agriculture is a measure of overhang effect of external debt on agriculture. The relationship between rD and agriculture is a measure of depressing effect of interest payment and principal due for repayment on agriculture. The relationship between interest payment on debt and agriculture is a measure of burden of interest payment of external debt on agriculture.

3.2.1 Specification of the Model

Recognizing the channel of interaction between agriculture and Dt,rD and r,the model for depressive effect of external debt on agriculture is expressed as:

$$Agric=\beta_0+\beta_1D_t + \beta_2rD + \beta_3r + \epsilon_2\dots\dots\dots(3.2)$$

Where β_0 =intercept; β_1 to β_3 are coefficient; ϵ_2 =error term

$$D_t <0;rD <0;rD<0; r<0$$

Agric=agriculture; Dt=external debt stock; rD=External debt service payments; r=interest payment on external debt; β_0 =intercept; β_1 = *coefficient of external debt stock*; β_2 =coefficient of external debt service payments; β_3 =coefficient of interest payments on debt.

Decision Rule

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If $D_t < 0$ then there is debt overhang on agriculture. If $rD < 0$ then external debt service has a depressing effect on agriculture.

3.2 Methodology

This study made use of secondary data sourced from Central Bank of Nigeria annual Reports and Accounts, National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) and internet sources. The researcher estimated the time series data with Auto-Regressive Distributive Lag (ARDL) technique. First, the researcher tested the time series data for unit root to determine the time properties of the data. Unit root test is a pre-test usually used to identify if a time series data are stationary or not, to prevent a spurious regression and ensure sound validity of the model. For this study, the researcher used Phillips-Perron test statistic.

Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) bounds testing co-integration.

If the variables are fractionally integrated at 1(0) and 1(I), ARDL bounds technique for co-integration is applicable. Pesaran, shin and Smith (Pesaran, shin & Smith, 2001), developed the Long run and short-run unrestricted ARDL bound testing approach in 2001. We specify **Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model** below as: $\Delta \ln \text{Dagric}_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \ln D_{t-1} + \beta_2 \ln rD_{t-1} + \beta_3 \ln r_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^k \alpha_1 \Delta \ln \text{Agric}_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^k \alpha_2 \Delta \ln D_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^k \alpha_3 \Delta \ln rD_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^k \alpha_4 \Delta \ln r_{t-i} + \mu_t \dots\dots\dots(3.3)$

ARDL bounds testing hypotheses is stated as:

H_0 : the variables are not co-integrated

H_1 : the variables are co-integrated

Decision rule: Reject H_0 if the computed F-statistic falls above the upper critical bounds at chosen level of significance and accept H_0 if otherwise. Do not Reject H_0 if the computed F-statistic falls below the lower critical bounds at chosen level of significance. Take no decision about H_0 if the computed F-statistic falls inside the lower and upper critical bounds at chosen level of significance. The short run relationship among the variables is specified as:

$$\Delta \ln \text{agric}_t = \sum_{i=1}^k \alpha_1 \Delta \ln D_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^k \alpha_2 \Delta \ln rD_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^k \alpha_3 \Delta \ln r_{t-1} + \lambda \text{ecm}_{t-1} + \mu_t \dots\dots\dots(3.4)$$

Where ecm_{t-1} is the short-run dynamic error correction factor, λ is the coefficient of ecm_{t-1} that measures the speed of adjustment in the short-run into the long run and μ_t is the white noise error term. If the coefficient of ecm_{t-1} is negative we then conclude that there exists short-run relationship between the independent variables and dependent variable. As a result, the study analysis will rely on short run results because of the advantages short-run results have over long-run results. Short-run results have the following advantages over long-run results:

- (a) short-run is a convenient model that corrects disequilibrium in short-run into long run;
- (b) Short-run results resolve the problem of spurious regression by taking into account the lag of error correction model (ECM) which eliminates trends from the model;
- (c) ECM fits into both general and specific approach to econometric model;
- (d) the error term in Short-run result is a stationary variable etc (Gujarati, 2004).

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4.0 PRESENTATION AND INTERPRETATION OF RESULTS

4.1 Presentation of Results

Pre-test

Table 4.1:PP Unit Test Result: Do not reject Ho, if $t^* > PP$ critical value

	1%crit	At Level	p-val		1%crit.	1 st difference	p-val	
DAGRIC	-3.57772	-3.460294	0.0136	1 (0)	-3.740446	-4.170583	0.0000	1 (1)
DS	-3.57703	-1.757028	0.3967	1 (0)	-3.581152	-8.466135	0.0000	1 (1)
Dt	-3.57772	211.3029	0.9999	1 (0)	-3.677837	-3.6000987	0.00310	1 (0)
R	-3.57772	-5.854072	0.0000	1 (1)	-3.581152	-5.715046	0.0000	1 (1)

Source: Researcher’s computation

Agriculture (agric) was not stationary at levels but stationary after the first difference and integrated of order one i.e. 1(1). External debt service (DS) was not stationary at levels but stationary after the first difference and integrated of order one i.e.1 (1). External debt outstanding(Dt) was not stationary at levels but stationary after the first difference and integrated of order zero i.e.1(0).Interest rate(R) was both stationary at levels and after the first difference and integrated of order one i.e.1(1).Since not all the variables were integrated of order one ARDL technique is more for analysis.

4.1.1 ARDL Bound Test

Based on the result in Table 4.2 we selected lag 1 as indicated by AIC, SC and HQ. We now present the result of ARDL bounds test to co integration in Table 4.3.

Table 4.2: VAR Lag Order Selection Criteria for the Model

Lag	LogL	LR	FPE	AIC	SC	HQ
0	-770.4040	NA	4.93e+09	33.66974	33.82875	33.72931
1	-661.2966	194.4958*	86316661*	29.62159*	30.41665*	29.91943*
2	-651.1445	16.33160	1.13e+08	29.87585	31.30696	30.41195

* indicates lag order selected by the criterion

LR: sequential modified LR test statistic (each test at 5% level)

The result in table 4.20 below shows that the variables are co integrated as the F-statistic of 13.796494 is greater than the 5% upper bound of 4.35. This implies that agricultural growth(Agric), external debt outstanding (Dt), external debt service payments (rD) and interest payment on foreign debt (r) have long run relationships, thus, necessitating the estimation of both short run and long run impact of DT, RD and R on Agric.

4.2 Interpretation of Results

The long run results presented in table 4.20 shows that external debt service payment (rD) and external debt stock (Dt) were statistically significant at 5% level of significance; while r, was not significant at 5%. Dt and r had negative influence on agriculture; but the influence of r was not statistically significant. External debt service payment (DS) had significant positive effect on agriculture (agric).The magnitude of relationships

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indicate that for every 1% increase in agriculture (agric) or economic development or improved welfare through agriculture, there was a depressing effect of .23% by external debt outstanding(Dt) and 0.000002% of interest payment on external debt. In addition, for every 1% in improved welfare based on improved agriculture (Agric.), external service payment (rD) contributed 1.14%.This result did not comply with theory. However, it indicates that repayment of external debt out grew improvement of agriculture. The negative sign on Dt and R was in compliance with the apriori; whereas the positive sign on rD does not agree with the apriori.

The Short run Results presented in table 4.20 indicate that the negative sign on Dt and R agreed with the apriori expectation; whereas the positive sign on rD was not in compliance with the apriori expectation. Dt and R had negative and depressing effects on agriculture in Nigeria. Dt and rD are statistically significant at 5% level of significance; whereas, R was not statistically significant at 5% level of significance. For every 1% increase in agriculture, external debt stock had a significant negative and depressing effect of 0.04% on agriculture.

The short run results presented in table 4.20, shows that external debt outstanding (Dt) and interest payment on foreign debt (r) had significant negative impact on agriculture (agric); while external debt service payments (rD) has significant positive impact on agriculture.

In the short run, except external debt service payment (rD), the rest of the explanatory variables were not statistically significant at 5% level of significance. Moreover, for every 1%improved welfare based on improved agriculture (agric), external debt outstanding (Dt) and interest payment on foreign debt (R) had negative and depressing effects of 0.04% and 0.0004% respectively. The coefficient of the error correction term was significant and negative with a value of about 0.168460. This implies that about 16.8 percent of the errors were corrected annually. The independent variables of the model jointly explained about 94.5516% of the variations in Agric as revealed by the coefficient of the R-squared adjusted value of 0.945516. The remaining 5.4484 % was error term. The probability of F-statistic value of 0.000000 means that the overall model is significant in explaining Agric based economic development in Nigeria. The Durbin-Watson statistic of about 2.078 indicates absence of serial correlation among the residuals of the variables.

Table 4.3: ARDL Bounds Test to Co integration for Model

Test Statistic	Value	K
F-statistic	13.796499	3
Critical Value Bounds		
Significance	I0 Bound	I1 Bound
10%	2.72	3.77
5%	3.23	4.35
2.5%	3.69	4.89
1%	4.29	5.61

Source: Author’s computation

The result in table 4.20 shows that the variables are co integrated as the F-statistic of 13.796494 was greater than the 5% upper bound of 4.35. This implies that Agric, DT, RD and R had long run relationship, necessitating the estimation of both short run and long run impact of DT, RD and R on Agriculture. We now present the short run and long run results in Table 4.21.

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Table 4.4: ARDL short run and long run results (dependent variable: Agric)

Short run		Result		
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(LDT)	-0.038595	0.01483601	-2.601441	0.018
D(LRD)	-0.191593**	0.081568	-2.348857	0.0236
D(R)	-0.00040	0.0008481	-0.471642	0.6396
CointEq(-1)	-0.168460**	0.075471	-2.232115	0.0310
Long run		Result		
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
LDT	-0.229106	0.0649264	-3.528703	0.0008
LRD	-1.137317**	0.493638	-2.303949	0.0262
R	-0.02702	0.0101325	-2.66667	0.0464
C	-0.218637	1.080974	-0.202259	0.8407
R-squared	0.950254	F-statistic	200.5730	
Adjusted R-squared	0.945516	Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000	
Durbin-Watson stat	2.078547			

Source: Author’s Computation

***, ** and * denotes significant variables of the model at 1%, 5% and 10% significance levels respectively.

Diagnostic Test of the Model

Table 4.5: Residual diagnostic tests of model adequacy of the Model

Breusch-Godfrey serial correlation LM test			
F-statistic	0.955205	Prob. F	0.3989
Obs*R-squared	3.244181	Prob. Chi-Square	0.1975
Heteroskedasticity test: Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey			
F-statistic	0.864218	Prob. F	0.6157
Obs*R-squared	15.88617	Prob. Chi-Square	0.5319
Jarque-Bera test of normality			
Jarque-Bera	2.150486	Probability	0.341215

Source: Computed by the authors using Eviews

The significance of this model is further confirmed by the B-G LM test of serial correlation. This is the second order condition. We now present the results of residual diagnostic tests of the model 3 on Tale 4.22.

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Table 4.6: Residual diagnostic tests of model adequacy for Model 3

Breusch-Godfrey serial correlation LM test			
F-statistic	0.955205	Prob. F	0.3989
Obs*R-squared	3.244181	Prob. Chi-Square	0.1975
Heteroskedasticity test: Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey			
F-statistic	0.864218	Prob. F	0.6157
Obs*R-squared	15.88617	Prob. Chi-Square	0.5319
Jarque-Bera test of normality			
Jarque-Bera	2.150486	Probability	0.341215

Source: Computed by the authors using Eviews

Tests critical values are compared at 5% level of significance

The result in Table 4.22 indicates that the model passed all the diagnostic tests of model adequacy as shown by the insignificant probability values of the F-statistics and observed r-squared of the serial correlation, heteroskedasticity and normality tests. This implies that the model did not suffer from any of the econometrics problems. The stability of the model was validated by the graph of the CUSUM test of stability in Figure 4.3 below. It could be seen that the CUSUM line appears within the acceptable region of the graph.

Figure 4.3: CUSUM Test of Stability for Model 3

5.1 Conclusion and Recommendations

5.2 Conclusion

External debt had overhang effect on agriculture both in the short run and over the long run. For every 1% increase in agricultural output, external debt outstanding had a depressing effect of 0.04%. Interest payment on foreign debt and principal due for repayment depressed agriculture. For every 1% increase in agriculture, interest payment on foreign plus principal due for repayment depressed agriculture by 0.2%. The cost of external borrowing depressed agriculture indicating the rising cost of investment. However, the relationship was not

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statistically significant at 5% of significance. Over the long run, external debt outstanding, external debt service payment and cost of contracting foreign debt had significant negative effect on agriculture in the reviewed period. Policy implications: this result implies the problems of extreme hunger, rising unemployment and acute poverty, suggesting difficulties in accomplishing sustainable development goals in 2030. It suggests much demand pressure and inflationary pressure in Nigeria.

5.2 Implications of Findings and Recommendations

Implications of the findings: 1.Nigeria's external burden from 1970 to 2025 has a depressive effect on agriculture; 2.such adverse effect of external debt on agriculture implied less agricultural infrastructure, technology, fertilizers etc.; 3.less productivity in agriculture and increased food scarcity; 4. Increased hunger and Nigeria's inability to accomplish Sustainable Development Goal of zero hunger in 2030. Hence, the author recommended as follows: government should ensure that all kinds of public borrowing should be project tied, giving more priority to agriculture. Investment in agriculture in Nigeria should be more of transfer of real resources rather than monetary income to avoid inflation.

To avoid monetary growths that accompany external borrowing, government should invest the larger portion of public borrowing in food production. Restrictive fiscal and monetary policies by government to set aside resources for debt repayment and avoidance of accumulation of arrears of repayment are appropriate recommendations. Government should combine contractionary fiscal policy and expansionary monetary policy to check the depressing effect of contractionary fiscal policy on growth. Government must see agriculture as a priority by transferring resources to this sector. Any policy reform targeted at reviving agriculture on a sustainable basis must first strengthen the capacity of the public sector in the provision of complementary inputs in infrastructure, improved financial intermediation in agriculture and publicly supplied goods. Despite the much-said concerning agricultural revolution in Nigeria by promoters of ideas of the present administration, much need to be done on agricultural in Nigeria. Nigerian agriculture is anemic and requires transfer of resources from other sectors. If Nigeria must accomplish Sustainable Development Goals in 2030, there is need for policy adjustment to reverse the negative of external debt on agriculture currently.

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